

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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(mainly English, Russian) within the framework of one communication. In linguistic literature, code-switching is defined as the phenomenon of switching from one language unit to another in the speech of people who speak two or more languages [2]. International research in the field of computational linguistics shows that the development of artificial intelligence models for the Uzbek language, which belongs to the group of “low-resource languages”, is a serious problem [3]. It is these three areas - the problem of neologisms, code switching and language resources - that constitute the main object of research in this article.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The problem of the digital transformation of the Uzbek language has been partially addressed in research in several areas. Below is a brief analysis of the existing literature on these areas - neologisms, code switching and language resources.

Neologisms and the digital environment. The emergence of new words and expressions in languages under the influence of digital technologies has been widely studied in international linguistics. For example, D. Crystal, in his fundamental research, analyzed the language of the Internet and its impact on the lexical system and showed that electronic communication has become the main generator of neologisms [1]. There are some works in Uzbek linguistics on this subject. In particular, Sh. Rahmatullayev described the mechanisms of formation of computer and Internet-related terms in the word formation system of the Uzbek language [4]. However, his research is mainly based on materials from the 1990s-2000s and does not cover the rapid digital changes of the last decade (social networks, messengers, online games). Also, the question of the reflection of modern neologisms in normative dictionaries and their relationship with the norm remains open.

Code-switching. The phenomenon of code-switching has been studied primarily as a natural feature of speech in bilingual and multilingual societies. One of the classic works is the work of K. Myers-Scotton, who substantiated the social motives of code-switching, the concepts of matrix language and incorporated language [2]. This phenomenon has been relatively poorly studied in Uzbek material. Although N. Mahmudov analyzed the features of the use of colloquial elements in speech, relying on explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language, he did not specifically study the specific forms of code switching in digital discourse (for example, mixed code in mobile applications and social networks) [5]. The speed of the user's transition from one language to another in the digital environment, the models of code switching in short messages and their pragmatic function have not yet been studied at the monographic level.

Artificial intelligence resources for the Uzbek language. In the field of computational linguistics and natural language processing (NLP), the Uzbek language is among the “low-resource languages”. Relatively little work has been done on the Uzbek language internationally. Abdurakhmonova and Tuliyeu analyzed the existing corpora for the Uzbek language (the National Corpus of Uzbekistan, the Educational Corpus of the Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies) in their articles and noted serious shortcomings in their size, annotation quality, and open access [3]. The authors also showed that the accuracy of morphological analyzers (e.g., UzMorph) and text classifiers in the Uzbek language is still not up to the required level. In another study, A. Sharipova studied the error rate of texts of Uzbek machine translation systems (Google Translate, Yandex Translate), and found that the incorrect transmission of forms related to agglutinative morphology is especially problematic [6].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. The material was a corpus of 500,000 words of texts taken from social networks (Telegram, Instagram) in 2022-2026, as well as existing dictionaries and NLP tools [3]. To identify neologisms, the corpus linguistics method was used, which was analyzed by the frequency of lexical units and word formation models. To study the phenomenon of code switching, 2,000 messages were content-analyzed and classified into types based on the Poplack typology [7]. In order to verify the effectiveness of artificial intelligence tools, Google Translate, Yandex Translate, and UzMorph were experimentally tested and evaluated by the BLEU metric and error rate [8].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The corpus analysis revealed a total of 1,247 neologisms used in Uzbek digital communication between 2022 and 2026. Of these, 848 (68%) are borrowings from English, 237 (19%) from Russian, and the remaining 162 (13%) originate from other languages or represent internally created Uzbek neologisms. The most

frequently occurring English-origin neologisms include post, like, repost, story, channel, bot, chat, video, selfie, trend, hashtag, comment, meme, stream, fake, and block.

The distribution across different word-formation models shows that direct borrowing without any morphological adaptation dominates, accounting for 52% of all neologisms (e.g., like, story, fake, repost). The second most productive model, at 31%, involves the addition of Uzbek derivational or inflectional suffixes to borrowed stems, resulting in hybrid forms such as like+la+moq (to like), post+la+moq (to post), and repost+qil+moq (to repost). Acronyms and abbreviations constitute 12% of the identified neologisms, including international tech terms like IT, UX, AI, VPN, as well as locally created abbreviations. Hybrid models that combine Uzbek and foreign elements within a single word (e.g., selfi+chik – a person who takes many selfies, layk+bo'l+di – it has been liked) represent only 5% of the cases but are growing in frequency, particularly among younger users aged 18–25.

A particularly problematic finding concerns orthographic variation. For instance, the English borrowing post was found in seven different orthographic forms within the corpus: post (standard), po'st, post (with Cyrillic influence), posta, po'st, and even pochta (where the meaning shifts toward “mail” in some contexts), along with the hybrid postka. Similar variation was observed for like (layk, layk, like, lyke) and comment (komment, comment, komentariya). This indicates the absence of any codified orthographic norm for digital neologisms in contemporary Uzbek [4].

When compared with early computer-related terminology from the 1980s–1990s (e.g., kompyuter, displey, fayl, printer), two significant differences emerge. First, the adaptation rate has decreased dramatically: whereas 85% of early computer terms underwent some form of phonological or morphological adaptation, only 48% of current neologisms show such adaptation. Second, the speed of diffusion has accelerated: the word like, for example, entered active usage between 2015–2017 and by 2020 had reached an 85% frequency rate in daily digital communication among Uzbek-speaking users under 35. This rapid diffusion leaves little time for normative institutions (such as the Uzbek Language Institute or terminological committees) to respond with standardized equivalents.

Code-switching was identified in 867 out of 2,000 analyzed messages, representing 43.35% of the total sample. Applying Poplack's typology [7], the distribution across switching types is presented in Table 1 below (Table 1).

Table 1.
Distribution of code-switching types in Uzbek digital discourse¹

Code-switching type	Proportion	Example from corpus
Lexical (single word)	58%	<i>Itimos bunga layk bosing</i> (Press like on this, please)
Phrasal	22%	<i>qalaysiz?</i> (How are you?)
Inter-sentential (between sentences)	15%	<i>Keldim. Bir daqiqa.</i> (I arrived. Wait a minute.)
Intra-sentential (within clause)	5%	<i>O'ylashimcha sen shunaqa qilmasliging kerak</i> (I think you shouldn't do that)

Beyond the typological distribution, several important patterns emerged. First, the dominant language pair is Uzbek-English, accounting for 71% of all code-switching instances, followed by Uzbek-Russian (22%), and Uzbek-English-Russian trilingual switching (7%). The predominance of Uzbek-English switching represents a significant shift from the early 2000s, when Uzbek-Russian switching was the norm in digital communication. Second, intra-sentential switching, although only 5% of cases, is the most structurally complex and requires the highest level of bilingual competence; it was observed almost exclusively among users aged 18–25 with higher education or international exposure.

The pragmatic functions of code-switching in Uzbek digital discourse are distributed as follows: emphasis or contrast (38%), expressing a concept for which the speaker feels the Uzbek equivalent is inadequate (31%), humor or irony (18%), and reducing social distance or signaling group membership (13%). The final function — group membership signaling — is particularly noteworthy. Among users aged 18–25, frequent code-switching functions as a digital identity marker, distinguishing “internet-savvy” users from older generations or those less integrated into global digital culture. This is supported by the age-based distribution: code-switching frequency reaches 61% among the 18–25 age group but drops to 28% among users aged 30–35. The sharp decline after age 30 suggests that code-switching in contemporary Uzbek is not merely a structural linguistic phenomenon but a generational and sociolinguistic one closely tied to digital socialization.

¹ Source: Author's elaboration.

Experimental evaluation of four NLP tools for Uzbek revealed significant performance gaps. Machine translation systems showed only moderate accuracy: Google Translate achieved a BLEU score of 42.3 for Uzbek-English translation, while Yandex Translate scored 38.7 [8]. For comparison, high-resource language pairs (e.g., English-French) typically achieve BLEU scores above 55–60. The most common error type across both systems — accounting for 55% of all translation errors — involves the incorrect segmentation and handling of Uzbek agglutinative morphology. For example, the Uzbek progressive form *Kelyapman* (I am coming) was incorrectly analyzed by several models as *kel + yap + man* (root + “do” + first-person) rather than the correct *kel + yap + man* where **-yap-** is a single progressive morpheme.

The morphological analyzer *UzMorph* achieved a word-level accuracy of only 67.2% on the test sample. Error analysis showed that performance dropped sharply on neologisms (accuracy: 41%) and borrowed words (accuracy: 53%), compared to native Uzbek vocabulary (accuracy: 78%). This is directly relevant to the earlier findings on neologisms and code-switching: NLP tools trained primarily on standard literary Uzbek cannot adequately process the hybrid, neologism-rich language of digital communication.

ChatGPT with Uzbek-language prompts produced grammatically correct sentences but expert evaluators rated their naturalness at only 3.2 out of 5. Typical criticisms included overly literal translations, unnatural word order, and failure to capture pragmatic nuances such as politeness levels and contextual appropriateness.

The root cause of these performance limitations is corpus size. International best practices suggest that a minimally viable corpus for developing NLP models for a morphologically rich language like Uzbek requires at least 10 million words of annotated text [3]. Currently, the largest publicly available Uzbek corpora range between 500,000 and 1,000,000 words — a factor of 10 to 20 times smaller than needed. This resource gap constitutes a structural barrier to the development of high-quality AI tools for Uzbek.

The analysis reveals systematic interconnections among neologisms, code-switching, and NLP resource limitations. First, the lack of standardized orthographic norms for neologisms encourages code-switching: users who are uncertain about how to write a borrowed term in Uzbek simply retain it in its original form or switch to the other language entirely. Second, frequent code-switching reduces the accuracy of NLP tools, as most models are trained on monolingual or near-monolingual corpora and cannot reliably process multilingual input. Third, the absence of robust NLP tools means that digital content in Uzbek is less searchable, less translatable, and less amenable to automated analysis, which in turn perpetuates the low-resource status of the language. These three dimensions thus form a self-reinforcing cycle that hinders the full digital transformation of Uzbek.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study set out to analyze the digital transformation of the Uzbek language across three interconnected dimensions: neologisms, code-switching, and NLP resource availability. Based on a corpus of 500,000 words extracted from Uzbek digital discourse (2022–2026), a content analysis of 2,000 messages, and experimental evaluation of existing NLP tools, the following main conclusions can be drawn.

First, Uzbek digital communication is characterized by a high density of neologisms, the majority of which (68%) originate from English. Direct borrowing without morphological adaptation dominates (52%), while hybrid forms combining English stems with Uzbek suffixes account for 31% of cases. A critical finding is the absence of orthographic norms: frequently used neologisms such as *post* and *like* appear in multiple variant forms within the same digital space. This orthographic variability creates inconsistency and complicates both human communication and automated text processing.

Second, code-switching occurs in 43.35% of digital messages, with lexical-level switching (single words) being the most common type (58%). The dominant language pair is Uzbek-English (71%), marking a historical shift from the Uzbek-Russian dominance of the early 2000s. Code-switching functions not only as a communicative strategy but also as a generational identity marker: its frequency is 61% among users aged 18–25 but drops to 28% among those aged 30–35. This indicates that code-switching in contemporary Uzbek digital discourse is fundamentally age-stratified.

Third, existing NLP tools for Uzbek perform significantly below international standards. Google Translate achieves a BLEU score of 42.3 (compared to 55–60 for high-resource language pairs), the morphological analyzer *UzMorph* has an accuracy of only 67.2%, and the primary barrier is the extremely limited size of available corpora — 10 to 20 times smaller than minimally necessary for robust model development [3]. The study further established that the three dimensions are not independent but form a self-reinforcing cycle: orthographic uncertainty regarding neologisms encourages code-switching, code-switching reduces NLP accuracy, and poor NLP resources perpetuate the low-resource status of the language.

The ongoing digital transformation offers a valuable opportunity for Uzbek to strengthen its position within its own communicative territory, enabling speakers to use their native language confidently alongside English

and Russian through increasingly supportive digital tools. Achieving this outcome is not only a linguistic goal but also an important contribution to digital equity and cultural sovereignty. With deliberate, evidence-based intervention, the current phase of rapid transformation can be channeled toward the development of a fully modern, digitally capable, and richly expressive Uzbek language fit for the 21st century.

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